

New species in Galeommatoidea (Bivalvia) from Namibia

Nueva especie de Galeommatoidea (Bivalvia) de Namibia

Michael L. ZETTLER* & Leon HOFFMAN**

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ABSTRACT

Four new species in the superfamily Galeommatoidea (Bivalvia) were found in sediment samples from the continental shelf and upper bathyal slope off Namibia, SW Africa: *Kurtiella namibiensis* n. sp., *Bornia walvisensis* n. sp., *Scacchia aartseni* n. sp. and *Scacchia huberi* n. sp. One live specimen of *Bornia walvisensis* n. sp. was brooding. A commensal relationship is likely between *Bornia walvisensis* n. sp. and the decapod host *Kraussillichirus kraussi* (Stebbing, 1900).

RESUMEN

Se han encontrado cuatro nuevas especies de la superfamilia Galeommatoidea (Bivalvia) en muestras de sedimentos de la plataforma continental y el talud batial superior frente a Namibia, suroeste de África: *Kurtiella namibiensis* n. sp., *Bornia walvisensis* n. sp., *Scacchia aartseni* n. sp. y *Scacchia huberi* n. sp. Un ejemplar vivo de *Bornia walvisensis* n. sp. se encontró incubando. Es probable que exista una relación comensal entre *Bornia walvisensis* n. sp. y el huésped decápodo *Kraussillichirus kraussi* (Stebbing, 1900).

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KEY WORDS: Mollusca, SW Africa, upper bathyal, shelf.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, África SO, batial superior, plataforma continental.

INTRODUCTION

The Leibniz Institutes for Baltic Sea Research (IOW) in Warnemünde and Senckenberg am Meer (SaM) in Wilhelmshaven investigate marine geology, ecology and biodiversity. The study of marine molluscs in the Atlantic is part of the biodiversity research. The marine environment off Namibia belongs to the Benguela Large Marine Ecosystem (BCLME), which is one of the world's largest coastal upwelling areas (see

MOHRHOLZ *ET AL.* 2014 and references therein). The IOW has a long tradition to investigate the effects of upwelling waters on the oxygen regime and its impact on benthic life (e.g. ZETTLER *ET AL.* 2009, 2013, ZETTLER & POLLEHNE 2013, EISENBARTH & ZETTLER 2016). An ongoing project dealing with this topic is EVAR (Effect of variability in physical forcing on macro- and microorganisms and the biogeochemical processes cat-

* Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research (IOW), Warnemünde, Germany, michael.zettler@io-warnemuende.de. Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5437-5495>

** Senckenberg am Meer, Wilhelmshaven, Germany, leon.hoffman@senckenberg.de. Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0205-186X>

Figure 1. *Kurtiella bidentata*, off Namibia, M157/30, 117 m. a-d: outer and inner view of shell, length 2.75 mm; e: RV hinge. Figure 2. *Kurtiella ovata*, off Namibia, M157/36, 317 m, outer and inner view of shell, length 2.8 mm.

Figure 1. *Kurtiella bidentata*, frente a Namibia, M157/30, 117 m. a-d: concha, vista externa e interna, longitud 2,75 mm; e: charnela de la valva izquierda. Figura 2. *Kurtiella ovata*, frente a Namibia, M157/36, 317 m, concha, vista externa e interna, longitud 2,8 mm.

alyzed by them) from which the last research trip M157 emerged and on the results of which the present study is partly based.

We herein propose four new bivalve species in the superfamily Galeommatoidea Gray, 1840 from offshore Namibia. Galeommatoidea Gray, 1840 is among the largest bivalve superfamilies in terms of species (HUBER, 2015). Major contributions on Galeommatoidea that are relevant for the Namibian fauna include those by BARTSCH (1915), TURTON (1932), BARNARD (1964), HUBER (2015)

and VON COSEL & GOFAS (2019). BARTSCH (1915) and TURTON (1932) described many new species from the Turton collection from South Africa and BARNARD (1964) provided a major review of South African species. HUBER (2015) provided a morphological review of genera in Galeommatoidea and incorporated its species in a single family Galeommatidae Gray 1840. VON COSEL & GOFAS (2019) provided a comprehensive inventory of West African tropical bivalves. Additionally, a significant number of authors added smaller contribu-

tions on subsets of Galeommatoidea; we will quote some of them herein.

GOTO *ET AL.* (2012) provided a molecular analysis of the superfamily Galeommatoidea and proved that the group is polyphyletic below the supra-familial classification and that its taxonomy needs to be reviewed. Six clades of species were identified based on molecular analysis; only species in Basterotiidae Cossmann, 1909 formed a single clade and hence supported a family. MOLLUSCABASE (2020) follows the familial classification by BIELER *ET AL.* (2010) who identified three families in Galeommatoidea: Galeommatidae, Lasaeidae and Basterotiidae. We herein follow GOTO *ET AL.* (2012) and consider the separation between Galeommatidae and Lasaeidae as taxonomically uncertain.

cruises of Alexander von Humboldt (AHAB8), Maria S. Merian (MSM07 and MSM18), Meteor (M122, M131 and M157) and Mirabilis (RGNO). Sediment samples were taken using van Veen grabs, multi-corers, box-corers and dredges. The sediment samples were sieved by washing with seawater on board retaining the fractions larger than 0.5 and 1 mm, respectively. The residues were fixed in formalin and later sorted out and determined in the laboratory. Selected shells and specimens were colour-photographed using a confocal microscope in IOW. Other selected shells were prepared for scanning electron microscope (SEM) imaging at IOW.

The type material is deposited at the Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt (SMF). Other reference material is kept at the IOW.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The material used in this study was taken off Namibia during several

Abbreviations used in the text:

H height; LV left valve; RV right valve; L Length; T tumidity (two valves).

SYSTEMATICS

Class BIVALVIA Linnaeus, 1758
Superfamily GALEOMMATOIDEA Gray, 1840
Family uncertain
Genus *Kurtiella* Gofas & Salas, 2008

Type species is *Kurtiella bidentata* (Montagu, 1803) by original designation.

Kurtiella bidentata (Montagu, 1803) (Fig. 1)

Mya bidentata Montagu 1803: 44-45.

Kurtiella bidentata: Gofas & Salas, 2008: 122-125, figs. 5-8.

Kurtiella cf. *bidentata*: Gofas & Salas, 2012: 64-67, figs. 1-2.

Material examined: Namibia • 340 live-collected specimens (many juveniles); 18.385°S, 11.922°E; 42 m; 12 May 2004; AHAB8/BE1; van Veen grab. • 8 live-collected specimens; 18.191°S, 11.841°E; 32 m; 12 May 2004; AHAB8/BE2; van Veen grab. • 3 live-collected specimens; 17.316°S, 11.723°E; 26 m; 05 Mar. 2008; MSM07/BE17; van Veen grab. • 1 live-collected specimen; 17.340°S, 11.602°E; 117 m; 01 Sep. 2019; M157/30; van Veen grab.

Remarks: We refer to GOFAS & SALAS (2008, 2012) for the description and distribution of the species. Shells from Namibia (Fig. 1) are most similar to those

from Europe (GOFAS & SALAS 2008: figs. 5-8). Morphological differences observed in shells from West Africa (GOFAS & SALAS 2016: figs. 1-2) are herein consid-

ered variability within one species with a wide eastern Atlantic distribution.

All finds from Namibia were made in silty or muddy bottom sediment. The

distribution of the species is hereby extended to Namibia; the overall latitudinal range is 71°N-20°S, the bathymetric range is 1-200 m.

Kurtiella ovata (Jeffreys, 1881) (Fig. 2)

Montacuta ovata Jeffreys, 1881: 698; pl. 61 fig. 4.

Kurtiella ovata: Gofas & Salas, 2008: 125-128, figs. 9.

Material examined: Namibia • 3 valves; 23.000°S, 13.317°E; 362 m; 28 Aug. 2019; M157/9; van Veen grab • 26 valves; 25.000°S, 13.733°E; 317 m; 06 Sep. 2019; M157/36; van Veen grab.

Remarks: We refer to GOFAS & SALAS (2008) for the description and distribution of the species. Shells from Namibia (Figs. 2a-d) are most similar to those from Europe (GOFAS & SALAS 2008: fig. 9). The similar species *Kurtiella tertia* Gofas & Salas, 2012 has thin elongated teeth in the right valve and rudimentary elongated teeth in the left valve.

ALLEN (2008) reported this species from off Namibia in 622 m, and its occurrence is hereby confirmed. The latitudinal distribution range in the eastern Atlantic is 36°N-25°S, the bathymetric range is 180-700 m (GOFAS & SALAS, 2008). Our record from Namibia was made in silty or muddy bottom sediment with high amount of dead shells. No living specimens have been found.

Kurtiella namibiensis n. sp. (Figs. 3-7)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:922A4D21-38D1-424E-B6A9-2CF9C2B26CDC

Type material: *Holotype*, Namibia • 1 life-collected specimen (Fig. 3); 23.000°S, 13.317°E; 362 m; 28 Aug. 2019; M157/9; van Veen grab; SMF 358956. *Paratypes* • 6 live-collected specimens (Figs. 4-7); same data as for holotype; SMF 358957.

Other material examined: Namibia • 8 live-collected specimens; 17.267°S, 11.275°E; 508 m; 01 Sep. 2019; M157/27; box-corer. • 2 live-collected specimens; 25.000°S, 13.549°E; 627 m; 04 Sep. 2019; M157/34, multi-corer. • 10 live-collected specimens; 25.000°S, 13.733°E; 317 m; 06 Sep. 2019; M157/36; van Veen grab.

Type locality: Namibia, off Walvis Bay, 23.000°S, 13.317°E, 362 m.

Etymology: The species is named after the type locality in Namibia.

Description: Small solid shell, equivalve, inequilateral, with oval outline, anterior, posterior and ventral margins gently curved, and obtuse and blunt umbo inclined posteriorly; both valves with two teeth in V-shape. Height 1.6 mm, length 2.0 mm, tumidity 0.9 mm (Fig. 3).

Prodissoconch with two stages. Prodissoconch I, oval with straight dorsal margin; sculpture uncertain by erosion; length 0.22 mm. Prodissoconch II, oval outline; smooth with growth lines; separated from dissoconch by a marked edge; length 0.6 mm (Fig. 7).

Dissoconch with convex anterior, ventral and posterior margins, most convex posteriorly; straightened anterodorsal and postero-dorsal margins, umbonal angle 120° (Figs. 3-6). External sculpture with numerous irregular commarginal growth lines of variable strength, coarser near ventral margin; fine irregular radial sculpture and irregular coarse branching radial ridges near anterior and posterior margins. Periostracum glossy, thin, light yellowish, translucent. Shell internally smooth and glossy; weak broad radial grooves near

Figures 3-7. *Kurtiella namibiensis* n. sp., off Walvis Bay, Namibia, M157/9, 362 m. 3: holotype, length 2.0 mm; 4: paratype, length 2.1 mm; 5: paratype LV, length 2.2 mm; 5c: detail of the hinge; 6: paratype RV, length 1.8 mm; 6b: SEM micrograph of the same valve, pallial line and muscle scars highlighted with white line; 6c: detail of the hinge; 7: paratype, length 1.7 mm, umbonal view, length of prodissoconch II 0.6 mm.

Figuras 3-7. Kurtiella namibiensis n. sp., frente a Walvis Bay, Namibia, M157/9, 362 m. 3: holotipo, longitud 2,0 mm; 4: paratipo, longitud 2,1 mm; 5: paratipo valva izquierda, longitud 2,2 mm; 5c: detalle de la charnela; 6: paratipo valva derecha, 1,8 mm; 6b: micrografía de barrido de la misma valva, línea palial y impresiones musculares resaltadas con línea blanca; 6c: detalle de la charnela; 7: paratipo, longitud 1,7 mm, vista umbonal, longitud de la prodissoconcha II 0,6 mm.

umbonal area; fine shallow radial grooves near margin; pallial line without sinus; muscle scars of equal size, inconspicuous; broad pallial margin; sharp, smooth shell margin. Straight hinge plates of moderate strength at 120° (Figs. 5a-b, 6a-b). Right valve with two nearly symmetrical pronounced teeth placed at 100°; posterior tooth slightly shorter and thicker than anterior tooth; deep central triangular ligament pit, width about 0.08 mm (Fig. 6c). Left valve with two symmetrical teeth, pointed, posterior tooth shorter and more pronounced; deep central ligament pit (Fig. 5c).

Animal unknown; no molecular sequence available.

Variability: Little variability observed; length up to 2.2 mm.

Differential diagnosis: The species can be differentiated by the obtuse umbo, rel-

atively large prodissoconch and external radial sculpture. The sympatric eastern Atlantic *Kurtiella bidentata* and the South African *Kurtiella kraussi* (Turton, 1932) have a subquadrangular outline and a more pointed umbo that is placed more posteriorly and they lack the radial sculpture. The sympatric eastern Atlantic *Kurtiella ovata* has an oval outline but a more pointed umbo that is directed posteriorly. The amphi-Atlantic *Kurtiella verrilli* (Dall, 1899) has been reported off Namibia by ALLEN (2000, 2008). That species has an angular outline with a strongly convex posterior margin and more pronounced umbo compared to the oval outline of *Kurtiella namibiensis* n. sp.

Remarks: All finds from Namibia were made in silty or muddy bottom sediment. The latitudinal distribution range is 17°S-25°S; the bathymetric range is 317-627 m.

Genus *Bornia* Philippi, 1836

Type species is *Bornia corbuloides* Philippi, 1836 accepted as *Bornia sebetia* (O. G. Costa, 1830) by subsequent designation.

Bornia walvisensis n. sp. (Figs. 8-15)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:2DAC439E-99C8-4FD3-99B5-2F608B3D50D1

Type material: *Holotype*, Namibia • 1 live-collected specimen (Fig. 10) 23.000°S, 13.683°E; 154 m; 26 Aug. 2019; M157/11; van Veen grab; SMF 358958. *Paratypes* • 6 live-collected specimens; same data as for holotype; SMF 358959.

Other material examined: Namibia • 1 live-collected specimen; 17.267°S, 11.501°E; 150 m; 15 Aug. 2011; MSM18/KU3; van Veen grab. • 1 valve; 17.264°S, 11.615°E; 102 m; 15 Aug. 2011; MSM18/KU4; dredge. • 2 live-collected specimens; 20.175°S, 12.710°E; 133 m; 24 Aug. 2011; MSM18/NAM004; van Veen grab. • 7 valves; 20.764°S, 12.833°E; 226 m; 01 Jan. 2016; M122/20515; box corer. • 2 valves; 20.718°S, 12.837°E; 182 m; 03 Jan. 2016; M122/20523; van Veen grab. • 1 live-collected specimen; 18.000°S, 11.583°E; 180 m; 02 Nov. 2016; M131/P3; van Veen grab. • 3 valves; 23.000°S, 13.683°E; 154 m; 25 Aug. 2019; M157/10; dredge. • 42 valves; 17.267°S, 11.724°E; 33 m; 31 Aug. 2019; M157/24; van Veen grab. • 2 valves; 17.340°S, 11.602°E; 151 m; 01 Sep. 2019; M157/28; dredge. • 20 valves; 17.262°S, 11.717°E; 42 m; 01 Sep. 2019; M157/29; dredge. • 1 valve; 17.340°S, 11.602°E; 117 m; 01 Sep. 2019; M157/30; dredge.

Type locality: Namibia, off Walvis Bay, 23.000°S, 13.683°E, 154 m.

Etymology: The species is named after the type locality Walvis Bay, Namibia.

Description: Small solid shell, equi-
valve, subequilateral, trigonal-ovate outline with straightened ventral, antero-dorsal and postero-dorsal margins, convex antero-ventral and postero-ventral edges

and pointed umbo; moderately inflated. Left valve with two cardinal and one lateral teeth; right valve with one cardinal and two lateral teeth. Height 1.6 mm, length 2.1 mm, tumidity 0.8 mm (Fig. 10).

Figures 8-15. *Bornia walvisensis* n. sp., Namibia. 8. LV, M157/24, 33 m, length 1.8 mm; 9. RV, same locality, length 1.9 mm; 10. LV of holotype, M157/11, 154 m, length 2.1 mm; 11. Live-collected specimen viewed from left side, MSM18/KU3, 150 m, length 1.5 mm (aa = anterior adductor muscle, e = eggs or larvae, ed = external demibranch, f = foot, pa = posterior adductor muscle, pl = pallial line); 12-15. M157/24 (12: LV, 2.0 mm; 13: RV, 1.8 mm; 14: LV, 1.6 mm; 15: RV, 1.7 mm); 14b: LV prodissoconch and hinge, 14c: LV hinge, 14d: detail of the LV prodissoconch I; 15b: RV prodissoconch and hinge, 15c: RV hinge.

Figuras 8-15. Bornia walvisensis n. sp., Namibia. 8. valva izquierda, M157/24, 33 m, longitud 1,8 mm; 9. valva derecha, misma localidad, longitud 1,9 mm; 10. valva izquierda del holotipo, M157/11, 154 m, longitud 2,1 mm; 11. Ejemplar colectado vivo visto del lado izquierdo, MSM18/KU3, 150 m, longitud 1,5 mm (aa = músculo aductor anterior, e = huevos o larvas, ed = demibranchia externa, f = pie, pa = músculo aductor posterior, pl = línea paleal); 12-15. M157/24 (12: valva izquierda, 2,0 mm; 13: valva derecha, 1,8 mm; 14: valva izquierda, 1,6 mm; 15: valva derecha, 1,7 mm); 14b: prodissoconcha I y charnela, VI; 14c: charnela, VI; 14d: detalle de la prodissoconcha I, VI; 15b: charnela y prodissoconcha I, VD; 15c: charnela, VD

Prodissoconch with two stages, light yellowish. Prodissoconch I, oval with straight dorsal margin; sculpture with irregular growth lines and irregular shallow round pits (diameter of pits approximately 1 μm) in central and umbonal area, irregularly branched radial ridges near the ventral margin; length 0.11 mm, height 0.09 mm (Fig. 14d). Prodissoconch II, oval outline; smooth with growth lines; separated from dissoconch by a marked edge; length 0.34 mm (Fig. 14b).

Dissoconch with convex antero-dorsal margin, postero-dorsal margin straight near umbo and convex posteriorly; rounded umbo, inclined posteriorly, umbonal angle 130°. Postero-dorsal margin more convex than antero-dorsal margin. External sculpture smooth with numerous very fine commarginal growth lines of variable strength, a few coarser lines near ventral margin. Periostracum glossy, thin, translucent. No lunula or escutcheon present. Shell internally rough with flat pustules and inconspicuous radial streaks in area from umbo to pallial line, matt; pallial line without sinus; muscle scars of equal size, clearly marked; area beyond pallial line with inconspicuous radial grooves of unequal strength; broad pallial margin glossy; sharp smooth shell margin. Anterior muscle closer to umbo than posterior one. Straightened hinge plates at 130°. Left valve with two straight cardinal teeth, the tooth below the umbo is shorter, a triangular gap between the teeth; one short lateral tooth obliquely placed on posterior hinge plate; deep oblique triangular ligament pit. Right valve with one strong, curved cardinal tooth and two lateral teeth of equal strength; oblique deep ligament pit.

Animal of live-collected specimens not evaluated; no molecular sequence available. Brooding phase in reproduction cycle evident from a set of eggs or larvae visible by transparency inside the mantle cavity.

Variability: Minor differences have been observed on the degree of roughness of the inside of the valves, and on an occasional slightly convex ventral margin; length up to 2.3 mm.

Differential diagnosis: A discussion of species classified in the genus *Bornia* have been provided by Huber (2015: 488-489); only three species from the Mediterranean, the adjacent Atlantic Ocean and the Canary Islands have been considered as valid representatives of the genus: *Bornia sebetia* (O. G. Costa, 1830), *Bornia canariensis* Hoeksema & Simons, 2011, and *Bornia aartseni* Gofas, 2012. *Bornia geoffroyi* (Payraudeau, 1826) is a much larger species with a deviating hinge and it should be classified in a different genus. *Bornia balalaika* Cosel, 1995 from western Africa has an angular outline and a different hinge with long lateral teeth.

The type species *Bornia sebetia* is twice as large as *B. walvisensis* n. sp.; the hinge of the former species shows a deep central indentation; the cardinal tooth in the left valve is proportionally shorter and stronger than in *B. walvisensis* n. sp.; the dorsal margins are more convex in *B. sebetia*; prodissoconch II is 0.45-0.50 mm in *B. sebetia* and 0.34 mm in the new species. *Bornia aartseni* has a very similar outline and size; its ventral margin is convex and the cardinal tooth in the left valve is squarish versus a curved tooth in *B. walvisensis* n. sp.; the prodissoconchs I and II are smaller (GOFAS 2012: 0.10 mm and 0.26-0.28 mm) in *B. aartseni* compared to those in *B. walvisensis* (0.14 mm and 0.34 mm). *Bornia canariensis* has approximately half the size of the new species and has a proportionally thick hinge; its prodissoconch II has a length of about 0.28 mm versus 0.34 mm in *B. walvisensis* n. sp.

Remarks: All finds from Namibia were made in silty or muddy bottom sediment. Species in *Bornia* appear to be brooding (GOFAS, 2012; this study: Fig. 11). *Kraussillichirus kraussi* (Stebbing, 1900) (Decapoda: Callichiridae) was found in 8 of the total 12 stations. Although a high diversity of possible hosts (burrowing invertebrates) are known for Galeommatoidea, including crustaceans, holothuroids, echinoids and sipunculans (LI ET AL. 2016), it is likely that *Bornia walvisensis* n. sp. is a commensal with this callichirid host. The latitudinal distribution range is 17.2°S-23°S; the bathymetric range is 30-250 m.

Genus *Scacchia* Philippi, 1844

Type species: *Tellina elliptica* Scacchi, 1833 accepted as *Scacchia oblonga* (Philippi, 1836), by subsequent designation.

Scacchia aartseni n. sp. (Figs. 16-20)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:852A5D5A-AFD3-4257-9B1E-2ED2F24AFC3E

Type material: *Holotype*, Namibia • 1 shell (Fig. 16); 22.982°S, 14.039°E; 138 m; 19 Aug. 2011; MSM18/WFB Boje; dredge; SMF 358960. *Paratypes* • 15 live-collected specimens; same data as for holotype; SMF 358961.

Other material examined: Namibia • 7 live-collected specimens; 17.316°S, 11.723°E; 26 m; 5 Mar. 2008; MSM07/BE17; dredge. • 6 live-collected specimens; 20.175°S, 12.710°E; 133 m; 24 Aug. 2011; MSM18/NAM004. • 21 live-collected specimens; 22.830°S, 14.503°E; 27 m; 26 Aug. 2011; MSM18/WFB1; van Veen Grab. • 27 live-collected specimens; 22.500°S, 14.381°E; 35 m; 18 Sep. 2011; MSM18/NAM-BE17; van Veen grab. • 7 live-collected specimens; 22.500°S, 14.314°E; 54 m; 18 Sep. 2011; MSM18/NAM-BE18; van Veen grab and dredge. • 6 live-collected specimens; 22.500°S, 14.201°E; 82 m; 18 Sep. 2011; MSM18/NAM-BE19; van Veen grab. • 1 live-collected specimen; 20.003°S, 12.850°E; 91 m; 4 Nov. 2016; M131/P7; van Veen grab. • 2 live-collected specimens; 20.001°S, 12.150°E; 280 m; 5 Nov. 2016; M131/P5; van Veen grab. • 4 live-collected specimens; 19.999°S, 12.858°E; 95 m; 10 May 2019; RGNO/20010; multi-corer. • 2 valves; 23.000°S, 13.683°E; 154 m; 26 Aug. 2019; M157/11; dredge. • 8 live-collected specimens; 23.000°S, 14.377°E; 130 m; 5 Sep. 2019; M157/41; van Veen grab and dredge. • 1 valve; 25.000°S, 14.653°E; 85 m; 6 Sep. 2019; M157/44; dredge. • 1 live-collected specimen; 25.000°S, 14.745°E; 54 m; 10 Sep. 2019; M157/45; van Veen grab. • 1 live-collected specimen; 25.000°S, 14.800°E; 33 m; 10 Sep. 2019; M157/46; dredge.

Type locality: Namibia, off Walvis Bay, 22.982°S, 14.039°E, 138 m.

Etymology: *Scacchia aartseni* n. sp. is named to commemorate Dr. Ir. Jacobus Johannes (John) van Aartsen († 2020) in appreciation of his contribution to the taxonomy and nomenclature of small molluscs and especially for his published studies on Galeommatoidea.

Description: Small fragile shell, equivalve, subequilateral, oval outline with convex margins and pointed prosogyrate umbo; moderately inflated. Both valves one short cardinal tooth placed obliquely below umbo; oblique triangular ligament pit. Height 3.8 mm, length 4.5 mm, tumidity 2.0 mm (Fig. 16).

Prodissoconch with two stages, translucent light yellowish. Prodissoconch II, oval outline; smooth with growth lines; separated from dissoconch by a marked raised edge; length 0.6 mm (Fig. 18).

Dissoconch with postero-dorsal margin rather convex and raised towards umbo; antero-dorsal margin straightened near umbo. External sculpture with numerous commarginal growth lines of variable strength, a few coarser lines at major growth stages. Periostracum glossy, thin, yellowish, translucent. No lunula or escutcheon

discernable. Bifurcating antimarginal riblets towards anterior and posterior margins; very weak radial markings in the centre. Shell internally smooth with inconspicuous radial streaks in area from umbo to pallial line, flat pustules near umbo; pallial line (without sinus) a chain of smooth rounded imprints of mantle (Fig. 16b-c); muscle scars of equal size; broad pallial margin, glossy, sharp smooth shell margin. Concave anterior hinge plate; convex posterior hinge plate. Internal ligament posterior to the umbo.

Animal unknown; no molecular sequence available.

Variability: Minor differences have been observed on the convexity of the anterior and posterior margins, and the strength of the radial sculpture; length up to 4.5 mm.

Differential diagnosis: *Scacchia zorni* van Aartsen & Fehr-de Wal, 1985, from off SW Europe and NW Africa has a

Figures 16-20. *Scacchia aartseni* n. sp., Namibia. 16: holotype, MSM18/WFB-Boje, 138 m, length 4.5 mm (a, b: LV; c, d: RV); 17: subadult shell (live-collected), RGNO/20010, 95 m, length 2.2 mm (a: LV; b, c: RV); 18: detail of the umbo of a RV, same locality, length of prodissoconch II 0.6 mm; 19, 20: shell from MSM18/NAM004; 19: RV; 20a, b: LV, inner view and hinge; 20c, d: RV, inner view and hinge.

Figuras 16-20. Scacchia aartseni n. sp., Namibia. 16: holotipo, MSM18/WFB-Boje, 138 m, longitud 4.5 mm (a, b: valva izquierda; c, d: valva derecha); 17: ejemplar subadulto (recolectado en vivo), RGNO/20010, 95 m, longitud 2,2 mm (a: valva izquierda; b, c: valva derecha); 18: detalle del umbo de una valva derecha, misma localidad, longitud de la prodisoconcha II 0,6 mm; 19, 20: concha de MSM18/NAM004; 19: valva derecha; 20a, b: valva izquierda, vista interna y charnela; 20c, d: valva derecha, vista interna y charnela.

more pointed umbonal outline and the anterior and posterior margins are more convex than *S. aartseni* n. sp.; the cardinal tooth of *S. zorni* is projecting straight down from the umbo whereas it is oblique in the new species; the sinuosity of the hinge line of *S. zorni* is far less than in the new species; length of *S. zorni* is up to 6 mm whereas *S. aartseni* n. sp. is only up to 4.5 mm (VAN AARTSEN & FEHR-DE WAL, 1985: 64-67). HUBER (2015: 143) examined the shells of a juvenile *Scacchia aartseni* n. sp. (2 mm) from Namibia as conspecific to *S. zorni*. The given images and the description of *Scacchia* sp. 2 in HUBER (2015: 144, 504) belong to *S. aartseni* n. sp. as well. The type species *Scacchia oblonga* is strongly inequilateral and it lacks the radial sculpture of *S. aartseni*. *Scacchia tenera* (Jeffreys, 1881) from off Western Europe lacks the radial sculpture and has a more pointed umbo (VAN AARTSEN &

FEHR-DE WAL, 1985: fig. 2 of lectotype). *Scacchia maura* van der Linden, 1996 from off NW Africa has a near equilateral outline but with a more pronounced round umbo; it lacks the radial sculpture present in *S. aartseni* and its cardinal tooth in the left valve is a rounded knob (VAN DER LINDEN, 1996: 58, figs. 1-3) rather than an elongated oblique tooth in the new species. The South African *Scacchia carifa* (Bartsch, 1915) is higher and more oblong and it lacks the radial sculpture. *Scacchia exserta* van der Linden, 1996 from off the Cape Verde Islands and Mauritania has an unusually protruding round umbo and lacks the radial sculpture.

Remarks: All finds from Namibia were made in silty or muddy bottom sediment. Nothing is known about its food source. The latitudinal distribution range is 17.3°S-25°S, the bathymetric range is 20-280 m.

Scacchia huberi n. sp. (Figs. 21-23)

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Type material: *Holotype*, Namibia • 1 shell (Fig. 21); 17.267°S, 11.724°E; 33 m; 31 Aug. 2019; M157/24; van Veen grab and dredge; SMF 358962. *Paratypes* • 16 live-collected specimen and 32 valves; same data as for holotype; SMF 358963.

Other material examined: Namibia • 1 live-collected specimen and 10 valves; 17.262°S, 11.717°E; 42 m; 1 Nov. 2019; M157/29; van Veen grab and dredge.

Type locality: Namibia, 17.267°S, 11.724°E, 33 m.

Etymology: *Scacchia huberi* n. sp. is named after Dr. M. Huber in appreciation of his comprehensive contribution to the taxonomy and nomenclature of bivalves.

Description: Medium-sized fragile shell, equivalve, subequilateral, oblong-oval outline with convex margins, frequently slightly flattened anterior, posterior and ventral margins; bold prosogyrate umbo inclined anteriorly; shell moderately inflated. Both valves with one small pronounced cardinal tooth below umbo and one elongated lateral tooth posteriorly; elongated ligament area. Colour white. Height 6.6 mm, length 7.0 mm, tumidity 2.8 mm (Fig. 21).

Prodissoconch with two stages, translucent. Prodissoconch I smooth, subcircular outline, inflated with pro-

truding edge; length 0.14 mm. Prodissoconch II, oval outline; surface glossy with growth lines; separated from dissoconch by a marked edge; length 0.5 mm (Fig. 22 of paratype).

Dissoconch with postero-dorsal margin more convex and slightly raised towards umbo; antero-dorsal marginally convex near umbo. External sculpture with numerous commarginal growth lines of variable strength, a few coarser lines at major growth stages; a fine regular radial sculpture of riblets and grooves of equal strength. Coarse, fibrous periostracum, matt opaque, greenish-brown. No lunula or

Figures 21-23 *Scacchia huberi* n. sp., Namibia, M157/24, 33 m. 21: holotype, length 7.0 mm (a, b: outer and inner view of LV; c: hinge of LV; d-f: umbonal, outer and inner views of RV; g: hinge of RV; h: sculpture of LV); 22: umbo of a paratype, length of prodissoconch I 0.14 mm, length of prodissoconch II 0.5 mm; 23: paratype, same locality, length 5.7 mm (a, b: inner and outer view of LV; c: RV).

Figuras 21-23 Scacchia huberi n. sp., Namibia, M157/24, 33 m. 21: holotipo, longitud 7,0 mm (a, b: vista externa e interna de la valva izquierda; c: charnela de la valva izquierda; d-f: vistas umbonal, externa e interna de la valva derecha; g: charnela de la valva derecha; h: escultura de la valva izquierda); 22: umbo de un paratipo, longitud de la prodisoconcha I 0,14 mm, de la prodisoconcha II 0,5 mm; 23: paratipo, misma localidad, longitud 5,7 mm (a b: vistas interna y externa de la valva izquierda; c: valva derecha).

escutcheon present. Shell internally smooth, glossy; inconspicuous radial streaks in area from umbo to pallial line; parallel to the pallial line is a string of small isolated indents where mantle was attached; pallial sinus absent; muscle scars of equal size; broad pallial margin; sharp smooth shell margin (Figs. 21b,f). Both hinge plates convex. Broad ligament gap between cardinal and lateral teeth (Figs. 21c,g).

Animal unknown; no molecular sequence available.

Variability: Minor differences have been observed on the convexity of the anterior and posterior margins; length up to 7 mm.

Differential diagnosis: We are somewhat uncertain about the generic classification of the new species. *Scacchia huberi* n. sp. is larger than other con-

generic species. The fibrous periostracum is not known from the species off western Africa and Europe or in the Mediterranean. *Scacchia carifa* (Bartsch, 1915) from SE Africa has similar outline but the shell is more fragile, its commarginal sculpture is finer and its periostracum is thin and not fibrous. *Scacchia subradiata* (Gould, 1861) from SE Africa is very similar to the type species *Scacchia oblonga*: inequilateral with a pointed umbo and a very fine commarginal sculpture. For a discussion of other congeneric species see the discussion under *Scacchia aartseni* n. sp.

Remarks: All finds from Namibia were made in silty or muddy bottom sediment of the River Kunene. Nothing is known about its food or ecology. The latitudinal distribution range is about 17°S-18°S; the bathymetric range is 30-50 m.

DISCUSSION

Small species in Galeommatoidea are more diverse than most other bivalve superfamilies and the inventory of West African species is far from complete yet. Our samples yielded six species in Galeommatoidea off Namibia of which four are new to science: *Kurtiella namibiensis* n. sp., *Bornia walvisensis* n. sp., *Scacchia aartseni* n. sp., and *Scacchia huberi* n. sp. Our stations scarcely sampled the large shelfal and bathyal sea bottom off Namibia and more new species can be expected when more systematic sampling is done targeting specific habitats involving host species in Axiidea (Decapoda) and others (see LI ET AL. 2016).

GOTO ET AL. (2012) indicated the polyphyletic nature of species in superfamily Galeommatoidea; there is little support to cluster species in the traditional families. They investigated 29 genera in 38 species of which only 3 species in *Basterotia* M. Hörnes, 1859 formed a single cluster. Apart from *Basterotia*, all other genera either have an uncertain familial status or should be classified under the family Galeommatidae as suggested by HUBER (2015) until

more extensive molecular studies on more species better define genera and families. The definition of additional species and genera based on morphology and/or molecular data will be important to unravel the biodiversity and systematics of this complex group.

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